

EARTH SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF GRAVITY DATA BY CORRELATION METHODS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the issue of interpretation of gravimetric data by correlation methods. As you know, there can be a correlation between geological and geophysical data, or, as they say, a statistical relationship. This connection can be studied by methods of mathematical statistics. Thus, correlations are established between geophysical and geological parameters, for example, between gravity anomalies and the depth of the geological boundary of interest. Such a correlation analysis is first carried out on a reference area with known values of geophysical and geological parameters. On the basis of the analogy principle, using the correlation links established on the standard, geological characteristics are predicted by geophysical parameters within a certain (forecast) territory. Statistical methods for constructing structural maps based on gravity data are mainly used in the modification of multidimensional regression analysis (MRA) and correlation methods for transforming anomalies (COMT). Software for the correlation analysis of gravity data has been developed at the Department of Geophysics of the ASOIU. The article presents the mathematical foundations and results of the forecast of the structural scheme of the surface of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the Northern Saatly area of the Middle Kura depression of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: correlation analysis, regression analysis, boundary prediction, correlation coefficient, regression equation, upper Cretaceous deposits.

Introduction

Interpretation of gravity data using mathematical methods is currently widely used to solve geological problems [8,1,7,2,3]. These methods are also used today [9]. Static methods for constructing structural maps based on a set of geological and geophysical information are mainly used in the modification of multivariate regression analysis (MRA) and correlation methods. The essence of MRA is to establish statistical relationships between the depths of various sediment complexes according to seismic (or drilling) data and Boogier anomalies and their transformants, and to extrapolate these relationships to areas not studied by seismic exploration or drilling [7,1,2,4,5]. Due to the fact that in geosynclinal conditions, to which the area under study belongs, due to difficult seismological conditions, unambiguous reference seismic data on the structure of the lower Mesozoic stage cannot be obtained, at the Department of Geophysics, a methodology has been developed for applying MRA using only a representative part of conditional seismic horizons (CSG) and detailed gravity survey data. In this case, the representative part is understood as that part of the CSG that coincides in plan with the curve of the local anomaly. The choice of such a measure is based on the fact that in the case of one contact boundary, the local structure of the surface under study in the gravitational field should be reflected in the plan with much greater accuracy than on a schematic structural map. The purpose of this paper is to apply correlation methods for inter-

preting gravity data to predict the surface of upper Cretaceous deposits in the Northern Saatly area of the Middle Kura depression in Azerbaijan.

Means and methods

Statistical methods for constructing structural maps based on gravity data are mainly used in the modification of multivariate regression analysis (MRA) and field separation correlation methods (COMT). The COMT technique compares favorably with trend analysis in that it allows one to extract from the observed field value the residual anomaly that is best correlated with the depth of the surface under study [8]. The idea of correlation methods for transforming anomalies, developed at the MUOG named after Gubkin (I.I. Shraibman, M.S. Zhdanov and O.V. Vitvitsky) lies in the fact that the observed gravitational field is presented in the following form:

$$G_{\text{obs}} = G_{\text{res}} + G_{\text{backg}} \quad (1)$$

Where G_{obs} is observed value of gravity; G_{res} is residual component of gravity; G_{backg} is the background component of gravity.

The background component of gravity is represented as a polynomial and is called the transformation polynomial:

$$G_{\text{backg}} = \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) \quad (2)$$

Here: a_p is a coefficient of the transformation polynomial; $f_p(x, y)$ is a basis functions depending on x , y , x^2 , xy , $y^2 \dots$; N is the dimension (length) of the transformation polynomial; x, y - coordinates of observation points.

The residual component of gravity is represented as:

$$G_{res} = \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} b_i j_i + c \quad (3)$$

Where b_i , c are the coefficients of the linear regression equation; K - number of geological and geophysical parameters; j - geological parameter.

The coefficients a_p , b_i , c are determined from the condition of the minimum standard deviation:

$$\varphi = \left[G_{obs} - \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) - \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} b_i j_i - c \right]^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (4)$$

What is possible provided:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial c} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial a_p} = 0 \quad (p \in N), (i=1, 2, \dots, k-1) \\ \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial b_i} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

By solving this system, we can determine the coefficients a_p , b_i , c .

This approach to finding coefficients is called COMT-A. Within the framework of correlation methods for separating fields, when finding regression coefficients, another approach is also possible (COMT-B), when a geological parameter (for example, H) is considered as a function of its residual component G_{res} . In this case, the coefficients are determined from the condition:

$$\Phi = \left[H - b(G_{obs} - \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) - c) \right]^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (6)$$

However, this approach greatly complicates the formulas for solving the system of equations.

It should be noted that it is rational to apply this technique in the case when the complex of deposits under study is well reflected in the $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$ field.

In the case when the studied sediment complex is poorly displayed in the $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$ field, such as a highly dislocated upper mesozoic sediment complex occurring below the "P" horizon (the eroded surface of the upper Cretaceous sediments), the multivariate regression analysis (MRA) method has proven itself well. The desired geological parameter H in this case is represented as a polyline consisting of the parameter $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$ and various transformants of the gravitational field. Suppose there are two parameters $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$ and Δg_5 , then H is represented in the following form:

$$H = a_0 + a_1 \Delta g_{Bouguer} + a_2 \cdot \Delta g_5 + a_3 \cdot \Delta g_{Bouguer}^2 + a_4 \Delta g_{Bouguer} \Delta g_5 + a_5 \cdot \Delta g_5^2 \dots (7)$$

As can be seen, the parameter involved here is the product $a_4 \Delta g_{Bouguer} \Delta g_5$. However, the use of such a parameter is illegal in the case of a pronounced gravitational background, since this leads to a strong increase in the intensity of the local anomaly and an increase in random noise. Therefore, it is more appropriate to use a parameter representing the use of a parameter representing the sum of $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$ and Δg_{loc} . In this case, the geological parameter is represented as a function:

$$H = f(\Delta g_{Bouguer} + \Delta g_{loc}) \quad (8)$$

When the local structure of the studied sediment complex is well characterized by several transformants of the gravitational field, it would be rational to choose the form of the polynomial as follows [3]. Let there be a surface of a sediment complex having regional (H_{reg}) and local (H_{loc}) components of occurrence depth. Then

the depth of occurrence of the studied complex H will be equal to:

$$H = (H_{reg} + H_{loc}) \quad (9)$$

The local component of the depth of occurrence can be represented as a polynomial:

$$H_{loc} = \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(\Delta g_i) \quad (10)$$

Where Δg_i are the local components of the gravity field.

If we consider the regional depth component as a linear function of $\Delta g_{Bouguer}$, that is:

$$H_{reg} = b \cdot \Delta g_{Bouguer} + c \quad (11)$$

That equality (11) can be represented as:

$$H = \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(\Delta g_i) + (b \cdot \Delta g_{Bouguer} + c) \quad (12)$$

As can be seen, these expressions resemble expression (1) in the case of the COMT-A method and expression (6) in the case of the COMT-B method. However, in contrast to them, here in the transformation polynomial, instead of the coordinates of the observation points (x , y), the values of the transformants of the gravity field Δg_i of the observed point participate. Expression (12) will be called the transform polynomial. Let's call the rest of the parameters:

f_p - are the basis functions depending on local anomalies; Δg_i are values of local gravity anomalies at the point under study; a_p are the coefficients of the transform polynomial; b, c are coefficients showing the relationship of the regional component of the depth of occurrence with the gravity anomaly.

Coefficients a_p , b , c can be determined from the condition:

$$\varphi = \left[H - \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(\Delta g_{loc i}) - b \cdot \Delta g_{Bouguer} - c \right]^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (13)$$

For the implementation of correlation analysis algorithms, the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU has developed the Fortran program MRA-COMT-COM.

The Middle Kur depression is covered by a large layer of Mesozoic sedimentary cover. The results are known only from the data of geophysical observations and exploration drilling. A large amount of geophysical work has been carried out in the Eastern part of the Middle Kur depression. At the first stage, exploratory geophysical surveys included seismic surveys and exploratory gravimagnetic surveys [6]. At the second stage, geophysical work was carried out mainly by CDPM seismic, detailed and high-precision gravimagnetic survey.

To predict the surface of the Cretaceous deposits in the Arabkubaly-Northern Saatly area, a seismo-gravimetric profile was compiled (Fig. 1). In this area, according to seismic survey data, isolines of the surface of Cretaceous deposits are noted, the depth of which reaches 4500 (seismic horizon SP-P). There are no seismic survey data at some places in this area. This is due to crop areas or impassable zones. An inverse correlation is observed between the gravity and seismic survey data on the depth of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits on the studied and neighboring area.

To establish a correlation between the values of the local anomaly Δg_{10} and the depth of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits and the feedback forecast, the correlation coefficient (R), the correlation moment (K)

between the geological and geophysical data, the coefficient of the regression equation (a) were calculated on

the computer and the forecast was made geological parameter H_{for} :

Figure 1. Seismic-gravimetric profile (Arabkubally-Northern Saatly area)

$N = 10$

H_i : 3.90, 4.00, 4.00, 3.90, 4.00, 4.00, 4.20, 4.40, 4.50, 4.60 km.

Δg_i : 6.00, 6.00, 5.90, 6.00, 6.10, 6.20, 6.20, 5.80, 5.40, 5.00 mGal.

K : -0.07

R : -0.82

a : 24.19

H_{np} , 4.03, 4.10, 4.03, 3.97, 3.90, 3.90, 4.17, 4.48, 4.84

To build a curve of predicted depth values, these values were first entered in the table (Table 1):

Table 1

	Predicted depth values									
N_i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Δg_i , mGal	6,0	6,0	5,9	6,0	6,1	6,2	6,2	5,8	5,4	5,0
H_i , km	3,9	4,0	4,0	3,9	4,0	4,0	4,2	4,4	4,5	4,6
H_{prog} , km	4.03	4.10	4.03	3.97	3.90	3.90	4.17	4.48	4.84	4.91

Based on the calculated results, the prediction boundary was calculated on a computer using feedback (Fig. 2) and this relationship was extended to the Arabkubally-Northern Saatly section, where there are Δg_{10}

values in the areal version. Below are maps of local gravity anomalies in digital form in 2D and 3D versions (Fig. 3-4).

Figure 2. Regression analysis of the seismic-gravity profile

Figure 3. Map of local anomalies in the Arabkubally-Northern Saatly area (2D) in units of mGal

Figure 4. Map of local anomalies in the Arabkubally-Northern Saatly area (3D) in units of mGal

Below are the results of the forecast of the depths of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits of the Arabkubally-Northern Saatly area:

Figure 5. Structural scheme of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits at the Arabkubaly-Northern Saatly site (2D) in units of km

Figure 5. Structural scheme of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits at the Arabkubaly-Northern Saatly site (3D) in units of km

As can be seen, there is an uplift of Cretaceous deposits in the North-Western and South-Eastern directions.

Conclusions:

1. The mathematical foundations of correlation methods for interpreting geophysical data and methods for establishing correlations between geological and geophysical data are considered, and ways of predicting geological parameters based on the results of correlation analysis are also considered.
2. Correlation methods for interpreting gravity anomalies are analyzed. Correlation methods for field separation, multivariate regression analysis and software for correlation methods for interpreting geophysical anomalies are considered. A rational method for establishing correlations between gravimetric and seismic data on the depth of occurrence of anomalous geological objects is described.
3. A correlation has been established between gravity and seismic survey data in the Arabkubaly-Northern Saatly area. For the first time, a feedback was established between the geological and geophysical

data of this area. Based on the established feedback, the surface of the Cretaceous deposits was predicted in those areas where there is no seismic data. A scheme of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits has been constructed, which has a South-West and North-East strike.

4. Using modern graphics software, 2D and 3D visualizations of the calculated depths of the surface of the Cretaceous deposits were made, which makes it possible to trace the boundary itself in more detail in space.
5. The results obtained can be used to guide further seismic and gravimetric studies in order to identify prospective areas of study in terms of oil and gas.

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